

Blog, blurb, twitter thread

Civic Data Cooperative 2023 Wrap-up

It's been a busy year for the Liverpool City Region Civic Data Cooperative. We've travelled the globe, launched many new projects, and worked with partners across the City Region and abroad on innovative data stewardship projects.

Check out a just a few highlights from our 2023 work below ↓

👏 We want to extend a massive thank you to all our staff, collaborators, and affiliate programmes in Liverpool and abroad.

🎉 Happy New Year to all, we can't wait to see what 2024 will bring!

It's been a busy year for the Liverpool City Region Civic Data Cooperative. We've travelled the globe, launched many new projects, and worked with partners across the City Region and abroad. Here is a small snapshot of our year in review

year in review highlights below.

January

Worked with NHS NorthWest Secure Data Environment to design secure processes for regional health data

Presented CDC plan at Involve UK workshop on sustainable public engagement

- CDC-affiliate Mental Health Research for Innovation Centre funding of £10.5 million announced
- Emily presented the CDC's Public Engagement Plan at the Involve UK workshop: 'How can data be informed by sustained and sustainable public engagement?'
- The CDC wrapped up its consultation with General Practitioners and GP Managers on Health Data Sharing Agreements in Cheshire and Merseyside
- The CDC worked with the NHS NorthWest Secure Data Environment to design the secure processes for regional health data
- CDC attended Wearable Tech of the Future in Newcastle run by the Internet of Caaring Things and National Innovation Centre for Aging

February

February saw the return of two core programmes for CDC:

- Core programme What's Your Problem 2023 focussed on men's mental health and student mental health
- Funded and launched 2nd Student Enterprise Programme with the University of Liverpool Careers Team focused on the cost-of-living crisis

March

- Emily and Emma (Capacity UK) opened Open Research Week 2023, presenting on the plan for the new CDC Round 'Ere project
- What's Your Problem continues - Data Shaping Sessions and Pitch Advice provided
- Work on the M-RIC Trustworthy Research Environment started

April

- CDC-affiliate Children Growing up in Liverpool (C-GULL), a longitudinal birth cohort study begins recruitment
- Colleagues attended the AI for multiple long-term conditions: Research Support Facility (AIM RSF) conference with the DynAIRx team

May

M-RIC launched with event attended by VC and MHM Chairs

What's Your Problem 2023 finished, awards seed funding to Mind Map and GigMate

Community Researcher training begins in Widnes for Round 'Ere

CDC-supported 'Bring Back the Night Bus' Project launched

Civic Data Talks launches

- What's Your Problem 2023 finished, awards seed funding to Mind Map and GigMate
- Round 'Ere finished community recruitment in Widnes
- Ellie and Em attend Stronger Things in London
- Gary attended the Software Sustainability Institute Unconference, with a focus on supporting career development for Research Software Engineering and other Research Technical Professional pathways
- Welcomed Vincy Huang to the CDC team as a Research Assistant working on the Digital Commons project
- EF attended LCR Innovation Summit at the Spine
- M-RIC launched with event attended by VC and MHM Chairs

June

- Community Researcher training begins in Widnes for Round 'Ere
- We hosted our first Civic Data Talks online seminar with Gary Leeming and Julian Tait
- The CDC team attends the Data Justice Conference in Cardiff. Gary and Emily present their work on data stewardship and public participation methods.
- CDC-supported 'Bring Back the Night Bus' Project launched
- Mental Health Mission chairs visit Liverpool to launch MRIC
- IB part of the Liverpool delegation to welcome Korean visit as part of the Connected Places Catapult UK-Korea city twinning programme

July

- CDC officially joined Cooperatives UK as an Associate Member
- Prof Iain Buchan signs letter of intent twinning the CDC with Busan Techno Park
- Round 'Ere community researchers interview over 200 Widnes residents about wellbeing and data

- First C-GULL baby born
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- CDC officially joined Cooperatives UK as an Associate Member
- CDC PI Prof Iain Buchan won the Florence Nightingale Award and travels to South Korea to sign a letter of intent twinning the CDC and affiliates with Busan Techno Park
- Civic Data Talks featured our Prof Iain Buchan
- Round 'Ere continues including a stakeholder workshop and a University of Liverpool Public Engagement blog
- EF attended LCR Air Quality round table event

August

- Round 'Ere community researchers out in Widnes interviewing residents on their thoughts on wellbeing
- First CGULL baby born
- The team took a well-deserved holiday

September

- Round 'Ere Phase 1 finished with two community data workshops
- Civic Data Talks featured Professor Simeon Yates and Dr Gianfranco Polizzi
- The first phase development of the M-RIC Trustworthy Research Environment was concluded with a launch event attended in person and virtually by over 100 people
- ER & EF attended Poet Streets workshop, Bootle
- OLS agreed to fund the Data Action Accelerator (£4.9M over 3years)

October

- CDC moves to new office in Liverpool Science Park
 - CDC team visit South Korea share work on data stewardship and innovation
 - Launch of Inclusive Participatory Data Stewardship project with the ESRC Digital Good Network and the Ada Lovelace Institute
 - CDC and partners nominated for the Praxis Auril Place-Based Knowledge Exchange Initiative of the Year
 - CDC team takes part in Coops UK Hackathon – launching our Data Commons project
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- Gary, Ellie, and Prof Buchan travelled to South Korea to share our work on data stewardship and innovation
 - Emily, Chantelle and Kaya travelled to London to launch the Participatory Data Stewardship project with the ESRC Digital Good Network and the Ada Lovelace Institute
 - Gary, Ellie, Vincy, and Emily travelled to London to take part in the Coops UK Hackathon – launching our Data Commons project

- The Civic Data Cooperative and affiliates were nominated for the Praxis Auril Place-Based Knowledge Exchange Initiative of the Year
- Civic Data Talks features Lara Groves from the Ada Lovelace Institute
- Gary presents our work at the Health City Design Congress
- Kaya, Chantelle, and Emily visit Bletchley Park to plan a new data literacy project in the Liverpool City Region
- Chantelle, Emma, Claire, Kateryna, and Rachel travelled to the Digital Health AI & Data Conference, CDC-affiliate DynAIRx project is presented
- Began recruiting GP practices in our Safe & Well Pilot areas – Toxteth and Halton
- M-RIC released [interim report](#)

November

- Civic Data Talks featured Dr Mhairi Aitken from the Alan Turing Institute
- We launched our new Community Data Conversations project
- Emily joined the Powered by Experience panel on participatory design presented by Capacity UK
- Emily joined the Connected by Data Design Lab at Hawkwood CFT in Stroud
- Bus Back Better project presented at the Club Health Conference
- Team attended ODI summit
- EF presented CDC at the Public Data for Economic Development workshop
- Praxis Auril awards dinner (finalist for Place Based Knowledge Exchange initiative of the year)
- IB hosted Korea Institute of Human Resource Development on Science and Technology delegation and presented CDC/CHIL

December

- We joined our affiliate programmes in launching the new Civic Health Innovation Lab offices at the Liverpool Science Park. Our new offices were opened by Professor Lucy Chappell, CEO of the NIHR, and attended by Joe Rafferty, CEO of MerseyCare, and Steve Rotherham, Metro Mayor of the Liverpool City Region
- EF attended inaugural LCR-Busan innovation partner forum
- CHIL hosted BPG Bio
- CHIL and M-RIC hosted Sir Robin Saxby
- Initiated project with Brownlow and Damibu to tackle the Refugee and Asylum access to appropriate health and wellbeing information
- EPSRC funded collaboration with UoM for technical capacity development linked to SDE
- Team takes well-deserved Christmas break

Infographic numbers

We launched/continued seven core projects. Plus 11? affiliate projects.

RE, WYP, Student Ent, CDT, Data Convo, Data Commons, CoP
Dynairx, MRIC, System P & AMRx, Night Bus, CGULL, Busan (PIF?), CHIL, , CIPHA, SEISMIC,
Safe & Well, Diaphram (led by Alder Hey), CPRD, NW SDE

We held 17 training sessions, events, or workshops.

Six RE, 2 WYP, 5 CDT, 1 CHIL, 1 MRIC, 2 SDE

- We hosted five Civic Data Talks seminars with XX attendees.
- We trained 14 community researchers who spoke with 212 LCR residents.

Our team collectively gave 30 talks or presentations on data innovation, stewardship, and innovation.

Involve Em, ORW Em, IWD Em, CoP launch Em, CDT Gary, CDT Iain, Coop UK Ellie, AP award Ellie, LCR Em, HCD Gary, PEP Panel Em, Iain SK X 3, DJ Conf x2 Gary Em, RE Vincy, RE Em x 2, WYP Ellie x2, SE Iain, SE Ellie, Edin Em, CA funded programmes (may) EF, EF data for economic development, EF Daresbury, EF Air Quality round table, IB Liverpool Calling (Eurovision), IB KIRD

Three new team members joined, xx affiliate team members joined.

Xxx SMEs engaged – ORCHA, Samwoo, Mind Map, Gigrate + 12 other applications, Daresbury presentation re AIM day ~10 SMEs in the room, Lyva Labs, ongoing support for Damibu – SBRI, (MRIC partners, Quantexa, Iqiva)

Other outcomes:

Partnerships with large businesses? (can we claim anything from MRIC here?)

Contribution to intelligence led, local health improvement programmes (research funding awarded? MRIC/Data Accelerator/Diaphram parent champions, Refugee and Asylum support)

Co-develop learning health system approach with NHS partners focussed on improving part of the system including patient experience (MRIC/Dynairx PPIE, RAAS?)

Support growth of digital and health informatics sector though access to appropriately consented data – Digital commons development? MRIC TRE/NW SDE?

Paper published?